

Large-scale multiactor training and mentorship programme to ASSist people with physical impairments in energy povERTy

D3.3 Finalised Multi language ASSERT e-learning platform Moodle

Co-funded by
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Report information

Purpose of the Report	Three lines executive summary/purpose of the current deliverable report
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Reviewers:	ECOSERVEIS, RETE ASSIST
Dissemination level:	Public
Date:	05/06/2026

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ABOUT ASSERT

The ASSERT project is a European initiative funded under the LIFE23-CETENERPOV framework, which will address the critical issue of energy poverty, particularly among people with physical disabilities.

The project goal is three-fold:

1. Ensure that policy makers at all levels of administrations, as well as energy practitioners and advisors, receive training on energy issues, including energy poverty, while fully accounting for the multidimensional nature of energy poverty and the broader context of clean energy transition.
2. Roll-out programmes to train front line workers on energy poverty and green energy solutions. Front-line workers to be trained include health and social care workers or other professionals who can help identify households inhabited by people with disabilities and experiencing energy poverty and provide them with advice and information on solutions to reduce energy consumption and access more affordable and innovative sources.
3. Offer targeted training courses for vulnerable households, including those with low digital skills. Such courses should enhance the energy and digital literacy awareness of households affected by energy poverty, enable them to better control their energy bills and actively participate in the clean and just energy transition.

ASSERT focuses on people with physical disabilities who often have higher energy needs and lower incomes and therefore are more susceptible to energy poverty and its effects. Addressing their needs can interrupt the vicious circle of aggravating health conditions because of unhealthy household conditions related to experiencing energy poverty.

The project will deliver an integrated target-specific training and mentorship programme for local policymakers and intermediaries and will equip them with essential skills and knowledge and support to implement sustainable energy solutions, while integrating energy poverty considerations into broader policy frameworks.

ASSERT consortium

N o	Participant organisation name	Short name	Countr y
1	AISFOR SRL	AISFOR SRL	IT
2	RETE ASSIST - ETS	RETE ASSIST - ETS	IT
3	ENERCOOP	ENERCOOP	FR
4	ASOCIACION ECOSERVEIS	ECOSERVEIS	ES
5	CITIZEN CROSSROADS	CCR	EL
6	ENERGEIAKO GRAFEIO KYPROU	CEA	CY
7	CLIMATE ALLIANCE - KLIMA-BUENDNIS - ALIANZA DEL CLIMA e.V.	CLIMATE ALLIANCE	DE
8	EUROPEAN NETWORK ON INDEPENDENT LIVING BRUSSELS OFFICE	ENIL	BE
9	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	NTUA	EL
10	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENERGY AND CLIMATE POLICY STICHTING	IEECP	NL
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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the **ASSERT Academy**, the multilingual e-learning platform developed within the ASSERT project to support the delivery of training programmes for municipalities and intermediary organisations. It documents how the ASSERT Academy was designed to act as a **comprehensive, multilingual, and accessible training hub**, supporting the wider objectives of the project to strengthen the capacity of policymakers and intermediaries.

Built on the Moodle LMS system, the **ASSERT Academy serves as the central digital environment where all project-related training materials, tools, and resources are hosted in an organised, accessible, and user-friendly way**. Moreover, through the ASSERT Library, the platform also provides access to a selection of external training materials, reports and tools related to energy poverty, disability, gender, and energy efficiency.

This report outlines the **structure, architecture, and functionalities** of the platform, providing a clear and concise guide for users, illustrating each section with figures to support navigation and understanding. It explains how the Academy is organised into key sections, including:

- The homepage.
- The training courses section for municipalities and intermediaries.
- Public deliverables.
- The ASSERT Library.

Finally, the document examines the platform's accessibility features, explaining the standards adopted, the tools used to evaluate compliance, and the specific measures implemented to ensure that all learners, including those with disabilities, can use the platform effectively.

1. ASSERT Academy: the e-learning platform

The ASSERT Academy is accessible online at the following link:

<https://assert.aisforacademy.eu/>.

The homepage will automatically open in one of the project languages (Catalan, Cypriot, English, French, Greek, Italian, Spanish) based on the user’s location. If necessary, users can switch language on the upper right corner of the page. The various language packs were installed to make the platform fully accessible to stakeholders from all pilot countries, as well as other European regions. By enabling course delivery in multiple languages, including English, the platform removes linguistic barriers and ensures broader participation.

Figure 1: Homepage upper section

At the moment of the publication of this report, it includes the following public pages:

1. Homepage
2. ASSERT Official publications
3. ASSERT Library
4. The registration page, required to access the courses
5. The courses pages with training materials for municipalities and intermediaries.

2. Platform Architecture

This section provides a brief, user-oriented overview of how to navigate ASSERT Academy.

The homepage is accessible by all users and requires no registration. As the ASSERT Academy is also the reference landing page of the project, the homepage needs to give users a general overview of the project and the training. For this reason, the following elements are found on the homepage:

1. Welcome to ASSERT.
2. Are you interested in joining the ASSERT course?
3. Our goals
4. How we work
5. ASSERT training courses
6. ASSERT Official publications
7. Discover the ASSERT Library
8. The pairs of involved municipalities and intermediaries
9. ASSERT Energy Disability Policy Tracker
10. About ASSERT
11. Page footer

Are you interested in joining the ASSERT course?

Click the button and fill out the form to register for the ASSERT platform.
Once you have completed your registration, you will be able to choose from the courses available on the platform.

To the form

Figure 2: Registration form

Our Goals

- Better understand the real needs of people with disabilities living in conditions of energy vulnerability.
- Improve local services, making them accessible, inclusive, and responsive to specific needs.
- Provide practical tools (guides, materials, consultations) to help families reduce energy costs and access available assistance more easily.
- Collect and analyze data to identify what truly works, guiding public policies and future interventions.

How we work

To achieve these goals, ASSERT is implementing a set of coordinated actions:

- Online training for municipal operators and intermediary organizations, with practical, easy-to-use content.
- Co-design meetings to jointly develop customized training tools and materials.
- Direct family support through home visits, energy kits, and personalized consultations.
- Exchange of experiences across participating territories, promoting good practices and innovative solutions.
- Impact evaluation through data collection and analysis before and after interventions, to adapt and improve actions.

Figure 3: Homepage midsection 1

ASSERT training courses

In the section below, you can discover the ASSERT courses dedicated to intermediaries and municipalities. Select your language and request registration!

<p>España Explorar</p> <p>Intermediarios Municipios</p>	<p>France Explorer</p> <p>Intermediaires Communes</p>	<p>Italia Esplora</p> <p>Intermediari Comuni</p>
<p>Ελλάδα Αναζήτηση</p> <p>Δήμοι Διαμεσολαβητές</p>	<p>Κύπρος Αναζήτηση</p> <p>Δήμοι Διαμεσολαβητές</p>	<p>Espanya Explorar</p> <p>Municipi Intermediaris</p>
<p>English (coming soon) Explore</p> <p>Municipalities Intermediaries</p>		

Figure 4: The training courses

ASSERT Official publications

Here you can find the official reports and publications issued within the project.

Enter

Discover the ASSERT Library

The ASSERT online library gathers resources on energy poverty and physical disability, providing useful materials for training, policies, and practical actions in a single accessible space.

Enter

Figure 5: Homepage midsection 2

The pairs of involved municipalities and intermediaries

The ASSERT project has involved 25 pairs of municipalities and intermediary organizations in a mentorship programme to develop specialized skills to address energy poverty, with a focus on supporting persons with physical impairments. Discover the involved municipalities and intermediaries!

Cyprus

1. Municipality of Nicosia and OPAK (Cyprus Paraplegic Organisation)
2. Municipality of Aradippou and KYSOA (Cyprus Confederation of Organisations for Disabilities)
3. Municipality of Athienou and SKE Athienou (Volunteers Council of Athienou)
4. Municipality of Ayia Napa and SMILE Project - Autism Support Famagusta
5. Municipality of Limassol and Pancyprian Association for the Rehabilitation of the Disabled (POAA) Limassol

France

1. City of Besançon (Energy Management Division) and APF France Handicap (Association of Paralysed People of France) Bourgogne Franche-Comté
2. City of Paris (Ecological Transition and Climate Division Department) and XXX
3. Lille European Metropolis (Private Housing Department) and Inhat
4. Greater Lyon Metropolis (Safety, Health and Environment Department) and APF France Handicap (Association of Paralysed People of France) AuvergneRhône-Alpes

Greece

1. Municipality of Komotini and Perpato Association
2. Municipality of Veroia and Ta paidia tis anoixis NGO
3. Municipality of Thessaloniki and Youth Council
4. Municipality of Athens and Sustainable Mobility Department of the Municipality's Urban Planning and Environment Directorate
5. Municipality of Kifisia and Community Center

Italy

1. Municipality of Parma and National Association of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities - (ANFASS) - Parma
2. Municipality of Arezzo and Foundation Arezzo Comunità
3. Municipality of Serrenti and Caritas Serrenti
4. Municipio Rome I and CER Le Vele

Spain

1. Energy Advice Points of Barcelona City Council, Social Rights Area and Union of Mothers in Functional Diversity
2. Social Action Department of Igualada City Council and Auria Private Foundation
3. Disability Care Service and Energy Esplugues of Esplugues City Council and Esplugues Without Barriers
4. Valencia Foundation Climate and Energy and Cystic Fibrosis Association of the Valencian Community
5. Network for Climate Shelters Barcelona and Municipal Institute for People with Disabilities, and ECOM

Figure 6: Pairs of Involved Municipalities and Intermediaries

ASSERT Energy Disability Policy Tracker

The Energy Poverty and Disability Policy Tracker aims to be a one-stop shop for information on energy poverty mitigation measures and disability-related support policies. It includes policies at national and local level for five countries i.e., Italy, Cyprus, Greece, France, and Spain.

[Discover more!](#)

Figure 7: Energy Disability Policy Tracker

About ASSERT

ASSERT is a project funded by the **European LIFE programme (LIFE23-CET-ASSERT)** and coordinated by **AISFOR**.

ASSERT Project

Co-funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union under project ID [ASSERT/101167584](#).
Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA.

Piloting partners: RETE ASSIST, ECOSERVEIS, ENERCOOP, Cyprus Energy Agency, Citizen Crossroads

Coordinator and other partners: AISFOR, CLIMATE ALLIANCE, European Network on Independent Living, National Technical University of Athens, Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy, Eurac Research

You are not logged in. ([Log in](#))

[Data retention summary](#)

[Get the mobile app](#)

Figure 8: Homepage Footer

3. ASSERT Official Publications

By entering the ASSERT Official publications section on the homepage, the user can find the project public deliverables and reports, linked to Zenodo.

The ASSERT publications are accessible online at the following link:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/assert-life/records>

Figure 9: Deliverables

4. ASSERT Library

By entering the ASSERT Library, the user can find a repository of training and educational resources currently available on energy poverty. A SWOT analysis has been conducted to evaluate and systematise the training and educational resources currently available in this section, with particular attention to how these resources incorporate, or fail to incorporate, the needs and perspectives of persons with disabilities. The assessment followed a rigorous multi-phase methodology combining qualitative and quantitative approaches.

Figure 10: Library overview

The resources are grouped into five main topics among which you can search:

1. Energy Poverty
2. Gender
3. Disability
4. Energy Efficiency
5. Summer Energy Poverty

Each thematic area has a **short explanation** to help users understand what they will find therein.

Energy Poverty ↗
 Energy poverty means not having enough access to affordable, reliable energy like electricity or heating. People experiencing energy poverty may struggle to keep their homes warm, cook food, or use basic appliances. It affects health, comfort, and quality of life, especially during extreme weather like hot summers or cold winters.
 This section gathers foundational and advanced resources that explore the concept of energy poverty, its causes, consequences, and policy responses. You will find materials that define energy poverty, explain its impact on different populations, and provide strategies for identification and mitigation. Resources are organized alphabetically and include tools, reports, training materials, and courses targeting municipalities, citizens, and intermediaries.

Gender ↗
 Gender refers to the roles, behaviors, and identities that society associates with being male, female, or other. It goes beyond biological differences and includes how people see themselves and express who they are. Gender can vary between cultures and individuals.
 This section focuses on the gendered dimensions of energy poverty. It highlights how women and gender-diverse individuals are uniquely affected by energy poverty and explores inclusive approaches to policy and service delivery. Resources are arranged alphabetically and include gender-sensitive guidelines, training materials, and case studies aimed at various target groups.

Disability ↗
 A disability is a physical, mental, or emotional condition that makes certain activities or tasks harder for a person. Disabilities can affect how someone moves, sees, hears, thinks, or interacts with the world. People with disabilities may need extra support or accommodations to do everyday needs.
 Here you will find materials addressing how energy poverty intersects with physical disability. This section includes resources that explore the specific barriers people with disabilities face in accessing energy and how these challenges impact health, mobility, and quality of life. Resources are alphabetized and tailored to support municipalities, intermediaries, and citizens in creating inclusive, accessible responses.

Energy Efficiency ↗
 Energy efficiency means using less energy to do the same task. It helps save money and reduce waste by making buildings, appliances, and vehicles work better without using extra power. For example, energy-efficient light bulbs use less electricity but give the same amount of light.
 This section focuses on improving energy efficiency as a key strategy to reduce energy poverty. It includes practical tools, technical guidelines, and educational materials that explain energy-saving measures and support sustainable housing upgrades. Resources are listed alphabetically and include content suitable for municipalities, intermediaries and citizens.

Summer Energy Poverty ↗
 Summer energy poverty happens when people cannot afford enough energy to keep their homes cool during hot weather. This can make it hard to use fans or air conditioning, leading to discomfort and health risks, especially for vulnerable groups like the elderly or children.
 This section addresses the less-known but critical issue of summer energy poverty. It includes reports, training materials, and adaptive strategies for heat resilience, especially for vulnerable populations. Resources are organized alphabetically and support all target audiences in understanding and addressing this seasonal risk.

Figure 11: Library categories

Inside each topic, materials are listed in alphabetical order.

Different types of resources are included:

2. Training Materials
3. Training Courses
4. Tools
5. Reports
6. Guidelines

Each resource is also tagged according to its intended audience: **Municipalities, Intermediary Associations** or **Citizens**.

Disability

Course Settings Participants Grades Reports More ▾

Disability Collapse all

A disability is the result of the interaction between people living with impairments and barriers in the physical, attitudinal, communication and social environment. For example, it is not the inability to walk that keeps a person from entering a building by themselves, but the stairs that are inaccessible to them. A disability is socially constructed as a disadvantage or restriction of activity caused by a society which takes little or no account of people who have impairments and thus excludes them from mainstream activity.

Here you will find materials addressing how energy poverty intersects with physical disability. This section includes resources that explore the specific barriers people with disabilities face in accessing energy and how these challenges impact health, mobility, and quality of life. Resources are alphabetized and tailored to support municipalities, intermediaries, and citizens in creating inclusive, accessible responses.

 Training course on co-designing accessible resources

This training program provides guidance on collaboratively designing educational courses that are accessible to people with disabilities. It covers inclusive design principles, stakeholder involvement, and practical strategies to ensure accessibility. (2022)

Language: English

Target: intermediaries

Type of document: training course

 Training course on human rights and disability

This training program by the Council of Europe focuses on human rights related to disability. It covers legal frameworks, rights protection, and inclusive practices to support persons with disabilities. (2024)

Language: English

Target: municipalities, citizens

Type of document: training course

Figure 12: Example of Resources on Disability

5. ASSERT Training Courses

Two training courses, one for municipalities and one for intermediaries, are offered in each piloting language and English, once the user registration is approved, with users able to self-enroll in the language of their choice, through the platform dashboard.

Figure 13: Dashboard with courses for intermediaries and municipalities

The overall aim is to provide participants with the information, insights and practical skills required to effectively address energy poverty and deepen awareness of the specific challenges faced by people in situations of energy poverty and by persons with disabilities. Through these courses, users will strengthen their comprehensive understanding of energy poverty and the available solutions, ultimately improving the municipalities' capacity to integrate appropriate measures into local action plans, and the intermediaries' capacities to assist people in need.

The content of the courses is adapted to the national contexts and structured around six main areas:

- 1 European and national regulatory frameworks on disability and energy poverty.
- 2 Energy poverty diagnosis.
- 3 The link between disability and energy poverty.
- 4 Practical and technical aspects of energy use and support mechanisms.
- 5 Inclusive communication.
- 6 Renewable energy use at the household level.

The platform allows partners to keep track of the progress of the users in the course by analysing data on accesses.

5.1. The structure of the training courses

The ASSERT training programme is designed to provide a clear, structured, and practical learning pathway on the intersection between disability, energy poverty, household energy use, and available support mechanisms. Its overall objective is to

strengthen the capacity of the project's target groups to better understand the specific needs of persons with disabilities in relation to energy vulnerability, and to support more inclusive, accessible, and effective responses at local level.

The two courses included in the programme are addressed to the actors involved in the implementation of the ASSERT approach: on the one hand, local authorities and municipalities, and on the other, intermediaries, NGOs, social workers, caregivers and other professionals working with vulnerable households. The courses do not treat disability and energy poverty as separate issues, but connect them through a practical perspective: how living conditions, health needs, accessibility barriers, administrative procedures, energy costs, and lack of information can interact and increase the risk of vulnerability. A specific strength of the programme is its attempt to combine conceptual knowledge with operational guidance.

Compared to the course for intermediaries, the one for municipalities includes 2 additional modules on M3.6 "Electricity market basis" and M4.5 "Good practices and case studies", and does not include M3.2 "How to navigate energy bills" and M3.5 "Relevant stakeholders and contacts".

Module 0: Introduction to the ASSERT Training Programme

The introductory module presents the overall structure of the training programme, explaining the course contents, learning pathway, methodology, evaluation system, certification process and participation rules. Its purpose is to provide participants with a clear understanding of how the course is organised and what they are expected to learn throughout the programme.

Module 1: Introduction to Disability

The first thematic module presents the concept of disability from a multidimensional perspective. It provides definitions of disability, including physical, sensory, cognitive, non-visible and episodic disabilities, while also explaining the evolution of the concept over time. Particular attention is given to the distinction between the medical model and the social model of disability, helping participants understand that disability is not only an individual health condition, but is also shaped by social, environmental, administrative and accessibility barriers.

The module also presents the main European policy framework on disability, including the Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021–2030 and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. This is complemented by an introduction to national and local frameworks, including existing policies, support programmes, initiatives and available local data in the pilot territories.

- **Module 1.1: Introduction to Disability** This lesson introduces the module's topics, objectives and learning expectations. It clarifies the main definitions of disability and presents different types of disabilities, including physical, sensory, cognitive, non-visible and episodic conditions. The lesson also explains the evolution of the concept of disability, with specific attention to the difference between the medical model and the social model.
- **Module 1.2: Introduction to the EU Framework on Disability** This lesson presents the evolution of European policies on disability in chronological order. Specific attention is given to the Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021–2030 and to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, adopted in New York in 2006.
- **Module 1.3: Introduction to the National Framework and Available Local Data** This lesson focuses on national and local disability frameworks in the pilot countries. It covers relevant policies, existing support programmes and initiatives, as well as available local data. The aim is to help participants understand how disability is addressed in their own institutional and territorial context.
- **Module 1.4: Dimensions of Disability** This lesson analyses disability through health, social and economic perspectives. It addresses disability assessment, the difference between disability and illness, legal guardianship, personal assistance, stigma, discrimination, gender, economic insecurity and disability-related costs. The lesson helps participants understand disability as a complex condition influenced by multiple factors, not only by medical diagnosis.
- **Module 1.5: Data Collection and Diagnosis** This lesson examines how disability-related data are collected, assessed and exchanged across different systems. It addresses European data collection, national diagnosis procedures, municipal databases, information exchange between social and health services, and the role of intermediaries in supporting people before formal disability recognition.

Module 2: Introduction to Energy Poverty

The second thematic module focuses on energy poverty and its relationship with vulnerability, inequality and social exclusion. It introduces the main definitions of energy poverty, energy inequality, energy vulnerability, and summer and winter energy poverty. The module also addresses the causes and consequences of energy poverty, including stressors, vulnerability factors and the broader impact on households.

The course then moves to the European policy framework, presenting the evolution of energy poverty as a policy concern and introducing the main EU-level references. This is followed by an analysis of national frameworks, including National Energy and Climate Plans, energy poverty mitigation strategies, subsidies, social tariffs, energy efficiency grants and national energy poverty observatories.

A specific section is dedicated to the local dimension of energy poverty. It addresses

the role of local authorities in implementing national policies, the relevance of the Covenant of Mayors, the role of local plans such as SECAPs or emergency support schemes, and the importance of successful local initiatives. These include mapping tools, platforms to identify energy-poor households, community-led projects, and replicable practices developed across Europe.

- **Module 2.1: Introduction to Energy Poverty** This lesson explains the concepts of energy poverty, energy inequality, energy vulnerability, and seasonal energy poverty, distinguishing between summer and winter conditions. The lesson also analyses the main causes, consequences, stressors and vulnerability factors.
- **Module 2.2: Introduction to the EU Framework on Energy Poverty** This lesson presents the European policy framework on energy poverty, showing how the concept evolves over time and how it becomes increasingly relevant within EU energy, climate and social policies.
- **Module 2.3: Introduction to the National and Local Framework** This lesson examines national and local policies and regulations related to energy poverty. It covers National Energy and Climate Plans, mitigation strategies, social tariffs, subsidies, energy efficiency grants, national observatories, local plans and the role of municipalities. It also introduces relevant stakeholders and highlights the importance of multi-stakeholder cooperation and citizen engagement.
- **Module 2.4: Dimensions of Energy Poverty** This lesson analyses energy poverty through health, social and economic perspectives. It addresses health risks, poor housing quality, administrative ambiguity between tenants, landlords and condominiums, stigma, gender, debt cycles, hidden costs, disconnections and evictions. The lesson helps participants understand energy poverty as a multidimensional condition, rather than as a purely financial issue.
- **Module 2.5: Data Collection and Diagnosis** This lesson focuses on why energy poverty should be assessed and how it can be detected. It introduces data collection methods, EPAH indicators and diagnosis tools, including thermal comfort assessment. The objective is to provide participants with a practical basis for identifying energy-poor households and understanding their needs.

Module 3: Practical and Technical Aspects of Energy Use and Available Support

The third module translates the knowledge acquired in the previous sections into practical and technical guidance. Its objective is to equip participants with basic tools to support households in understanding energy consumption, navigating bills, identifying accessible home adjustments, accessing financial support, contacting relevant stakeholders and exercising consumer rights.

- **Module 3.1: Basics of Energy Use** This lesson introduces the basic principles of household energy use and energy efficiency. It addresses simple low-cost

actions to reduce consumption, common domestic problems such as poor insulation, inefficient appliances, humidity and mould, and the relative consumption of different household appliances. It also considers how disability-related needs may affect energy consumption.

- **Module 3.2: How to Navigate Energy Bills** This lesson provides practical guidance on how to read and explain energy bills in simple language. It covers the purpose of energy bills, who sends them, what households pay for, and the main sections of a bill, including customer information, billing period, consumption, costs and payment details. It also explains basic consumption units such as kWh and cubic metres, linking them to daily household activities.
- **Module 3.3: Accessibility Home Adjustments** This lesson introduces the topic of accessibility-related home adjustments, with a connection to later project activities on interventions to reduce energy poverty. It provides a first basis for understanding how home conditions and accessibility needs can influence energy vulnerability and the type of support required.
- **Module 3.4: Financial Support Mechanisms** This lesson presents the main financial support mechanisms available to address energy poverty, with specific attention to measures for people with disabilities. It covers social tariffs, renovation grants, bonuses, subsidies for accessible appliances and basic information on how households can apply for support.
- **Module 3.5: Relevant Stakeholders and Contacts** This lesson maps the main local actors involved in supporting vulnerable households, including energy agencies, NGOs, municipalities, One-Stop Shops, caregivers, medical professionals and public departments dealing with social, health and energy issues. The aim is to clarify who does what and how households can be referred to the right service.
- **Module 3.6: Electricity Market Basics** This lesson introduces basic concepts related to the electricity and gas markets, including TSOs, DSOs, prosumers, wholesale trading systems and the role of market actors. The purpose is to help municipalities and intermediaries understand how energy prices are formed and how market fluctuations can affect citizens.
- **Module 3.7: Consumer Rights** This lesson focuses on energy-related consumer rights, including the right to energy, access to clear information, accessible bills, simplified administrative procedures, access to metering data and formal complaint mechanisms. The lesson also addresses accessibility issues that may affect people with disabilities when interacting with energy suppliers, DSOs or public authorities.

M4: Connecting Disability to Energy Poverty

This module establishes the critical link between disability and energy vulnerability. It explores how persons with disabilities often face a "double burden": higher energy needs, due to the use of assistive medical devices, the need for specific thermal regulation, or increased time spent at home, coupled with lower average incomes and higher living expenses.

- **M4.1 Introduction** The course begins with a comprehensive presentation of the module's topics, objectives, and learning expectations. The lesson provides a detailed explanation of the triggers linking disability to energy poverty, supported by practical examples. These are divided into structural obstacles (economic and administrative barriers) and technical obstacles related to specific needs, such as hearing or physical impairments and autism. Particular attention is given to "non-discretionary energy use," such as the power required for life-sustaining medical devices or the specific heating needs of immobile persons. The module also features a "myth-busting" activity to expose implicit biases and introduces the academic wheel of privilege to explore intersectionality. This allows participants to understand how factors like gender, ethnicity, and age intersect with disability to compound the experience of energy poverty.
- **M4.2 Transport poverty** This section expands the scope of vulnerability by addressing transport poverty and its intersection with disability. The module provides crucial information on the difficulties persons with disabilities face when navigating both urban and rural environments to access support services for energy efficiency or financial aid. It highlights how a lack of accessible and affordable transport options can become a significant barrier to escaping energy poverty, as residents may be physically or financially unable to reach the very services designed to assist them.
- **M4.3 Interventions to reduce EP** This module outlines the conceptual framework for understanding how energy poverty impacts the safe, autonomous living of people with disabilities. It diagnoses the systemic communication barriers and fragmented institutional coordination gaps currently experienced by municipalities. It highlights the critical role of Disabled People Organizations (DPOs) as trusted intermediaries in documenting lived needs and seasonal risks. It offers actionable strategies for local governments to build inclusive eligibility rules, accessible energy advice, and robust emergency preparedness protocols.
- **M4.4 Wrap-up** As the module nears its conclusion, a synthesis section is provided to consolidate the learning journey. This sub-module acts as a functional "checklist of action points," allowing participants to review the key takeaways and practical steps identified throughout the lessons. It serves as a bridge between theoretical knowledge and operational application in the field.
- **M4.5 Good practices and study cases** The final instructional sub-module focuses on inspiration through proven success stories. It details good practices in labor integration, showcasing policies such as municipal programs.

M5: Disability-Inclusive Communication

Effective energy renovation and support programs are only successful if they are accessible to everyone. This module focuses on the principles of inclusive and "Easy-to-Read" communication, ensuring that information regarding energy rights, efficiency measures, and available subsidies reaches persons with diverse cognitive,

sensory, or physical abilities.

The module provides practical tools for designing communication campaigns that avoid stigma and promote empowerment. Key topics include the use of plain language, accessible digital formats, and multi-channel strategies that consider different levels of digital literacy. By mastering these techniques, practitioners can foster trust and ensure that persons with disabilities are not only recipients of information but active, informed participants in the energy transition process.

- **M5.1 Using inclusive language** Language is the first step toward inclusion. This sub-module introduces the core principles of inclusive communication and the specific terminology required to engage respectfully with all citizens. A key focus is placed on the conceptual difference between "disability" and "functional diversity," providing participants with the linguistic tools to navigate these terms accurately. By establishing a professional and respectful vocabulary, the course ensures that communication avoids stigma and promotes the dignity of every individual involved in the energy renovation process.
- **M5.2 Using inclusive language (pt.2)** Building on the previous section, this sub-module explores the nuances of contemporary communication strategies. It provides a detailed explanation of the difference between people-first language (e.g., "a person with a disability") and identity-first language (e.g., "a disabled person"). Through concrete examples, participants learn when and why these different approaches are used, helping them to adapt their communication style to the preferences and cultural contexts of the communities they serve.
- **M5.3 Universal design** This section shifts toward the practical formats of information delivery. It provides a brief but essential description of the different formats of communication and the overarching principles of Universal Design. A significant portion of the module is dedicated to the Easy-to-Read (ETR) format, a specialized methodology designed to make complex technical information—such as energy audits or financial contracts—understandable for people with cognitive disabilities or low literacy levels.
- **M5.4 Institutional communication** The final thematic sub-module addresses the broader organizational and institutional level. It focuses on material creation and adaptation, offering "talking techniques" to improve the accessibility and clarity of information in user services. Furthermore, it details how to integrate inclusive communication into energy poverty and disability protocols and plans. The module also covers the design of awareness campaigns and the importance of creating synergies with academic, environmental, and media partners. By building these multi-sectoral networks, institutions can ensure that the message of an inclusive energy transition is amplified and reaches the most isolated or vulnerable households.

M6: Renewable Energy Sources for Domestic Use

The final module shifts the focus toward technical and sustainable solutions specifically tailored for the domestic environment. It provides an overview of the main renewable energy technologies, such as solar photovoltaic systems, solar thermal, and heat pumps, analyzing their feasibility and benefits for residential buildings.

A specific focus is placed on how these technologies can be integrated to increase the energy autonomy of households involving persons with disabilities. The module explores the role of "Prosumers" (producers and consumers) and the potential of Energy Communities to lower costs and provide a stable energy supply. Practical guidance is offered on assessing the technical requirements of a home and navigating the transition from fossil fuels to clean energy, ensuring that domestic upgrades lead to improved comfort, reduced environmental impact, and long-term savings.

- **M6.1 Introduction and benefits** The module establishes a technical foundation by introducing the basics of photovoltaics, explaining the composition of a solar system, how it converts sunlight into electricity, and the fundamental concepts of power and production. Beyond the mechanics, this section emphasizes the dual value of small-scale renewable installations, highlighting both the economic benefits of reduced utility bills and the environmental impacts of lowering a household's carbon footprint.
- **M6.2 Different types of electricity valuation** This sub-module explores the various ways citizens can engage with renewable energy production. It begins with individual self-consumption, detailing the principles, advantages, and technical criteria such as grid connection and the distribution of energy. The sub-module then introduces Plug & Play solar panels as an accessible, all-in-one solution, teaching users how to size their kits, where to install them, and how to navigate safety regulations. Furthermore, the lesson covers collective self-consumption, explaining how groups of residents can organize and share energy production. To help participants navigate these options, the module provides a comparative guide based on technical requirements, current national regulations, and cost-benefit analyses, enriched by real-world feedback from households and municipalities.
- **M6.3 Existing financial incentives** To support the practical take-up of renewable energy, this section provides an overview of the various financing and support mechanisms available. It explores national and local subsidies, specialized aid for low-income households, and innovative models such as group purchasing, third-party investment, and "energy as a service." By understanding these financial tools, participants can better bridge the gap between the initial investment costs of renewable systems and long-term energy savings.
- **M6.4 RES-Energy poverty nexus** The final thematic sub-module addresses the social and territorial integration of clean energy. It specifically analyzes how Renewable Energy Sources (RES) are compatible with and relevant to the unique energy needs of people facing disability and energy poverty. The

course explores how local authorities can develop a community-based approach to energy production, using concrete examples of initiatives and Energy Communities. This section demonstrates that when implemented with a social focus, renewable energy acts as a catalyst for inclusion and local development.

Course Assessment

To support a structured learning progression and verify the acquisition of the key concepts throughout the ASSERT training programme, there is an online quiz for each module. Completing and passing this quiz is a mandatory step for participants to demonstrate competency and successfully pass each respective module.

6. Accessibility

6.1 Accessible design

The ASSERT Academy has been designed with accessibility at its core. To ensure that all learners, including those with disabilities, can fully benefit from the training, the platform adopts a simple, intuitive, and user-friendly structure. Its straightforward layout, clear language, and essential-only content are intentional choices that help remove barriers and make the learning experience inclusive, effective, and accessible to the widest possible audience.

Moodle is WCAG 2.1 AA compliant, meaning that Moodle meets the respective accessibility criteria. Whether you are an educator, learner, developer, or system administrator, Moodle LMS authoring and evaluation tools are endorsed by WCAG as perceivable, operable, understandable, and compatible.

All design and layout choices were informed by evaluations carried out through [a dedicated platform developed by the Italian National Research Council \(CNR\)](#), which assesses the accessibility of websites and digital documents according to the international WCAG guidelines defined by the International Web Association. To ensure full visual accessibility, AISFOR applied a colour checker to calculate adequate contrast ratios between foreground and background elements, improving readability for users with visual impairments. In addition, since many users rely on screen readers or text-to-speech (TTS) software to navigate digital environments, all materials were structured to ensure compatibility with assistive technologies. Moodle, the open platform used for hosting training modules, offers built-in accessibility features, including optimized navigation flows and an essential “skip-to-content” function, enabling people with low vision or blindness to access information seamlessly.

Moreover, the training courses will also be integrated with national sign language interpretation.

Through these measures, AISFOR ensures that training resources and policy tools are inclusive, usable, and accessible to all stakeholders, including the most vulnerable groups.

6.2 Accessibility plugin

An accessibility plugin that allows users to customize the visual appearance of a Moodle to suit individual preferences appears throughout the Moodle site on all pages (including the login page) as an accessibility symbol button in the lower-right corner of the page. Clicking on the button produces a panel that contains the widgets that are available on the site. The base pack of widgets includes widgets

for text colour, background colour, font face, font size, kerning, letter spacing, line height, link highlighting and image visibility. The colour widgets are designed to let the user choose their preferred colours without being restricted to a small selection of palettes.

Figure 14: Accessibility Button

Assert Consortium

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/10/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** LIFE-2023-CET **Coordinator:** AISFOR SRL